

A Study of Copper(II) Complexes of Fluorescein Part I.

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The magnetic and thermal data of the two copper complexes $[\text{Cu}_2\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_9]_n$; $\text{Cu}_3\text{C}_{100}\text{H}_{78}\text{O}_{41}$ with fluorescein indicate an interaction between metal atoms through hydroxy bridging but the behaviour does not follow the pattern expected for dimeric interaction. The insolubility of the two complexes in known solvents establishes that the complexes are not dimeric but polymeric. Magnetic measurements and electronic spectra show a square planar symmetry for the two complexes. X-ray diffraction data for copper (II) sulphate pentahydrate and its fluorescein complex indicate that the copper complex possesses its distinct crystal structure. Thermal data reveal the hydroxy bridging in the complexes and the solid state studies hint at the polymeric and anti-ferromagnetic behaviour. The semiconducting properties of the two complexes support this conclusion.

FLUORESCEIN is a ligand possessing lactoid and quinoid forms in equilibrium in the solution state. The ligand molecule contains coordinating oxygen at three positions, namely, the carbonyl group, the hydroxyl group and the carboxyl group. A study of metal complexes of fluorescein was undertaken with a view to investigate the semiconducting properties, if any, of these. This article describes the magnetic, spectral, thermal and semiconducting behaviour of two copper complexes of fluorescein. The established structure of the ligand is given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Lactoid Structure of Fluorescein.

Experimental

Preparation of metal complexes :

Copper(II) fluorescein complex was precipitated as a brownish red compound by adding 0.1 M solution of CuSO_4 to 0.1 M alcoholic solution of fluorescein. The pH was adjusted between 5.8 to 6.0. The precipitate was dried at 120° .

Analysis :

	C	H	Cu
Found	45.12	3.02	24.18
Calculated for	45.52	3.06	24.12
$[\text{Cu}.\text{Flen}.\text{(OH)}_2.\text{(H}_2\text{O)}_2]_n$			

The copper nitrate derived complex was brown and was precipitated in a similar manner as above and dried at 120° .

Analysis :

	C	H	Cu
Found	48.64	2.94	20.65
Calculated for	48.82	3.17	20.68
$\text{Cu}_3(\text{Flen})_5(\text{OH})_8(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8$			

(Flen stands for ligand fluorescein).

Both these complexes were insoluble in all normal solvents.

Magnetic, spectral and other measurements :

The magnetic measurements from liquid air upto the room temperature and above were taken on a Gouy balance at T.I.F.R., Bombay. The standard calibrant used was $\text{HgCo}(\text{CNS})_4$.

The solution and reflectance spectra were taken on Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer with MgCO_3 as a standard for reflectance spectra. Infrared spectra of the complexes were taken on Perkin Elmer 137-1281 infracord. The KBr pellet technique and the Nujol mull method were employed. Conductivities of the complexes in DMF, nitromethane and acetonitrile were measured on LKB 3216 conductivity bridge. The cell constant of the built in cell was 0.0997 cm^{-1} .

Semiconducting properties of the complexes were studied on a GR 1608-A impedance bridge. The energy gap values were calculated by using the expression

$$\rho = \rho_0 \exp \left(\frac{-E_a}{kT} \right)$$

where E_a is the activation energy. The complexes were pressed into pellets at a pressure 6,000 psi and the breadth of the pellets varied between 0.265 to 0.296 cms. The diameter of the pellets was nearly

constant and varied slightly between 1.321 to 1.319 cm. The results were recorded at I.I.T., Kanpur in Dr. C. N. R. Rao's laboratory.

Thermal degradation studies were done on a Stanton's automatic thermo-recording balance at Punjab University, Chandigarh.

Results and Discussion

Table I A and B record the electronic absorption spectra of $[\text{Cu}_2\text{Flcn}(\text{OH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_n$ and $\text{Cu}_8(\text{Flcn})_5(\text{OH})_8(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8$ with probable assignment given in the last column. The spectral data appear to be substantially in favour of square planar stereochemistry for Cu(II) in view of the observations of Bannister

show that both these complexes exhibit anomalous Curie-Weiss behaviour in this that they do not exactly conform to the antiferromagnetic pattern. The pattern resembles somewhat to that observed by Hatfield and Bungar³ in their study of copper complexes with Schiff's bases containing OCH_3 and NO_2 group as substituents. The probable explanation of this magnetic behaviour is that planar molecules of the complexes are stacked in the solid state so that the bridging oxygen atom from an adjacent dimer is positioned over copper ion of the molecule in question. The square planar nature of complexes will, in all probability, facilitate this positioning and Hatfield and Bungar consider that intermolecular interactions could be transmitted through these linkages which may be responsible for anomalous magnetic behaviour observed in such complexes.

TABLE I(A)—ELECTRONIC ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF $\text{Cu}_8(\text{FLCN})_5(\text{OH})_8(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8$

	$\bar{\nu}$, cm^{-1}	ϵ (molar)	Assignment
Solid, Diffusion reflectance	30,300	—	${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \leftrightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$
	25,980	—	
	21,980	—	${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \leftrightarrow {}^2\text{B}_{2g}$
	11,110 to 10,970	—	${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \leftrightarrow {}^2\text{A}_{1g}$
Solution $1.1 \times 10^{-2} M$ in Nitromethane.	26,320	98	${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \leftrightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$
	12,900	50	${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \leftrightarrow {}^2\text{A}_{1g}$

TABLE I(B)—ELECTRONIC ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF $\text{Cu}_2\text{FLCN}(\text{OH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$

	$\bar{\nu}$, cm^{-1}	ϵ (molar)	Assignment
Solid, Diffuse reflectance.	27,400	—	${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \leftrightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$
	25,320 (Sd)	—	
	21,980	—	${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \leftrightarrow {}^2\text{B}_{2g}$
	11,110 to 10,810	—	${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \leftrightarrow {}^2\text{A}_{1g}$
Solution $1 \times 10^{-2} M$ in Nitromethane.	21,740	165.0	${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \leftrightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$
	17,390	206.8	${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \leftrightarrow {}^2\text{B}_{2g}$
	11,770(Sd)	28.2	${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \leftrightarrow {}^2\text{A}_{1g}$

and Cotton¹. Donoghue and Drago² obtained two reflectance bands at 378 nm and 750 nm for the complexes of copper studied by them which they consider characteristic of square planar stereochemistry for Cu(II). The diffuse reflectance data for the two copper complexes investigated by the present author. 455 nm, 380 nm ($\epsilon = 98$), 455 nm, 460 nm ($\epsilon = 165$) are indicative of square planar stereochemistry for these two copper complexes.

The curves representing the relation between molar susceptibility and temperature for the two complexes

Though the two copper complexes studied here could not be considered strictly dimeric, if it is assumed that in the polymeric molecule the copper-copper-interaction is essentially between the two copper atoms through hydroxy bridges, one may plot the curves for μ_{eff} vs kT/J using the data provided by Earnshaw and co-workers⁴. From these [$J = -208 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for $\text{Cu}_2\text{Flcn}(\text{OH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ and $J = -165 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for $\text{Cu}_8(\text{Flcn})_5(\text{OH})_8(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8$] it may be inferred that in these two complexes magnetic data rule out, though not completely, the existence of pure dimeric antiferromagnetic interaction.

Again, following the method of Hatfield *et al.*⁵, if equilibrium constant (K eq) for the two copper complexes at different temperature are calculated, the plots of $\log K_{eq}$ vs $1/T$ instead of showing a straight line, as was observed by these authors, show a curvature. The equilibrium constants for the reaction [singlet \rightleftharpoons triplet] were calculated from the magnetic data. The mole fractions of molecules in each state were calculated from μ_{eff} values. In all the calculations the singlet state was considered to have moment of zero B.M. and the moment for the triplet state was estimated from the expressions of $\mu = g[S(S+1)]^{1/2}$, g being taken as 2.05. Here the decreasing values of the μ_{eff} are indicative of copper-copper interaction as was observed by Hatfield Muto *et al.* in the study of some copper complexes.⁶

The infrared spectral patterns (Table 2) of the two copper complexes of fluorescein are similar indicating similar metal ligand coordination in the two complexes. The significant shifts, of infrared-frequencies assigned to -OH, -COOH and C-O groups in fluorescein is an indication of coordination between the metal and the ligand molecules through these positions.

The conductivity data (Table 3A and B) which in the case of $[\text{Cu}_2\text{Flcn}(\text{OH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_n$ is in favour of 1 : 1 electrolyte, favours a neutral electrolyte in the case of $\text{Cu}_8(\text{Flcn})_5(\text{OH})_8(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8$. In view of the polymeric nature of the complexes it is likely that the conductivity data may not provide reliable information.

TABLE 2—INFRA-RED DATA FOR $\text{Cu}_2\text{Flcn}(\text{OH})_8(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ AND $\text{Cu}_8(\text{Flcn})_5(\text{OH})_8(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8$

$[\text{Cu}_2\text{Flcn}(\text{OH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_n$ Wave number cm^{-1}	$\text{Cu}_8(\text{Flcn})_5(\text{OH})_8(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8$ Wave number cm^{-1}	Fluorescein, the ligand	
		Wave number cm^{-1}	Assignment
1080*	1090*	920	i) associated carboxyl group.
1170 (hydroxy bridges)	1175		ii) OH out of plane bending of acid dimer.
1265	1267	1235	C-O stretching.
1595	1600	1588	i) aromatic ring.
		1625	ii) antisymmetric COO^- stretching. quinoid carbonyl or aromatic ring.
		1675	i) associated carboxyl group.
			ii) quinoid carbonyl.
3320	3400	2500–3500	

* Assinged M–OH frequencies in polynuclear complexes.

X-ray study of Cu(II) sulphate pentahydrate and $[\text{Cu}_2\text{Flcn}(\text{OH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_n$ does not justify any firm conclusion regarding the crystal structures of the complex. It, however, shows that the complex possesses its distinct X-ray pattern. The diffraction data for copper sulphate pentahydrate and the complex is given in Tables 4 and 5. A trial and error method suggested by Henry, Lipson and Wooster⁷ for cubic, tetragonal and hexagonal systems was used.

TABLE 3—CONDUCTIVITY DATA OF $\text{Cu}_8(\text{Flcn})_5(\text{OH})_8(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8$ AND $\text{Cu}_2\text{Flcn}(\text{OH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$

Solvent	Concentration	ΛM ($\text{cm}^2\text{mole}^{-1}\text{ohm}^{-1}$)
{Complex :—		
$\text{Cu}_8(\text{Flcn})_5(\text{OH})_8(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8$		
Nitromethane	$1.24 \times 10^{-2}M$	11.48
	$0.83 \times 10^{-2}M$	16.92
	$0.16 \times 10^{-2}M$	26.40
D.M.F.	$1.80 \times 10^{-3}M$	19.42
	$0.48 \times 10^{-3}M$	6.94
	$0.26 \times 10^{-3}M$	23.60
{Complex :—		
$\text{Cu}_2\text{Flcn}(\text{OH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$		
Nitromethane	$1.08 \times 10^{-2}M$	68.3
	$0.90 \times 10^{-2}M$	74.6
	$0.16 \times 10^{-2}M$	83.0
D.M.F.	$1.26 \times 10^{-3}M$	84.6
	$0.98 \times 10^{-3}M$	94.2
	$0.42 \times 10^{-3}M$	96.2

TABLE 4 - X-RAY DATA FOR COPPER SULPHATE PENTAHYDRATE.

CAMERA : 14 CM DEBYE-SCHERRER. TARGET Fe K_α

No.	Intensity	d in Å	No.	Intensity	d in Å
1	1	5.567	8	1	3.263
2	2	5.393	9	2	3.019
3	1	5.139	10	1	2.828
4	10	4.659	11	2	2.721
5	9	3.922	12	1	2.637
6	7	3.624	13	4	2.382
7	1	3.500	14	2	2.010

TABLE 5—X-RAY DATA FOR THE COMPLEX $\text{Cu}_2\text{Flcn}(\text{OH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$

CAMERA : 14 CM DEBYE-SCHERRER. TARGET Fe K_α

Intensity	$\text{Sin}^2\phi$ obsd.	$\text{Sin}^2\phi$ calcd.	hkl	d in Å
3	0.0445	0.0449	101	9.187
5	0.0587	0.0584	200	7.995
5	0.1155	0.1168	220	5.699
2	0.1328	0.1314	300	5.316
1	0.1503	0.1508	112	4.998
2	0.2242	0.2201	321	4.092
1	0.2342	0.2336	400	4.004
10	0.2488	0.2482	410	3.883
8	0.3468	0.3457	213	3.289
1	0.4313	—	—	2.950
6	0.5405	0.5432	204	2.635
9	0.6248	0.6289	541	2.451
1	0.6258	—	—	2.449
2	1.1190	—	—	1.832

Tetragonal $a = 8.017 \text{ \AA}$; $c = 5.564 \text{ \AA}$.

In this connection observation made by Charles⁸ is worth noting. He found that the copper chelates derived from $(\text{CH}_3\text{CO})_2\text{CHCH}(\text{COCH}_3)_2$ had a degree of polymerisation of about five but unfortunately the molecular weight could not be determined (as in the present case) due to insolubility in normal solvents. However the X-ray diffraction showed the product to be crystalline. Thermogravimetric analysis and sealed tube pyrolyses show detectable weight losses occurring between 250° and 350° . The decomposition was found to be of zero order. Thermal analysis of the two copper complexes in the present investigation shows that the decomposition is of first order in both the cases, the values⁹ being 7.1 and $7.05 \times 10^{-5} \text{ sec}^{-1}$.

The electrical conductivity study of the two complexes in solid state suggests that the conductivities are in the semiconducting range activation energies for the two complexes being for $[\text{Cu}_8(\text{Flcn})_5(\text{OH})_8(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8]_n$ 0.55 and 0.21 eV and for $[\text{Cu}_2\text{Flcn}(\text{OH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_n$ 0.49 and 0.28 eV. This range is indicative of antiferromagnetic behaviour in complexes.

Actually Slater's original assumption¹⁰ of the insulating ground state for materials because of the doubling of the periodicity of the lattice due to

antiferromagnetism could be extended in this case to see if a temperature-dependent energy gap disappears at the transition temperature¹¹. This approach has great appeal when the transition temperature corresponds also to Neel point. However, the main difficulty is that the theory predicts it is to be valid only for an exactly half-filled band and it is not possible to establish this in the case of the two complexes studied.

The breaks in the conductivity plots appear to show that there are some subtle structural changes at temperatures (329° and 342°K) where discontinuities are found.

Thermal degradation studies of $\text{Cu}_8(\text{Flcn})_5(\text{OH})_8 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_8$ show that at about 130° the loss on 193 mg of the sample corresponds to nearly eight molecules of water. At 205°, the thermal data reveal further loss of four molecules of water presumably from OH groups which form the hydroxybridging of copper atoms. The loss at 350° can be attributed to the decomposition of the fluorescein ligand and thereafter the constant weight is due to the oxide formation. The loss on 234 mg sample at 120° roughly corresponds to two molecules of water. At 210° the loss of 6 mg is probably due to a loss of molecule of water while at 490° the loss seems due to the decomposition of the ligand molecule. At 600° a constant weight is attained.

The two samples were magnetically investigated at room temperature 27° after heating them in a muffle furnace at the temperatures at which significant change in weights were noted in thermal studies. The temperatures in the muffle furnace were regulated by a Sunvic dial and the samples were cooled in a desiccator to room temperature in an atmosphere of nitrogen. In the discussion below, the χ_M value of water is taken to be -12.96×10^{-6} and that of ligand -155.2×10^{-6} the unit being taken as 1×10^{-6} . The complex $\text{Cu}_8(\text{Flcn})_5(\text{OH})_8 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_8$ showed an increase of molar susceptibility of order of 120 units at 130° corresponding to a loss of nearly eight molecules of water. A further increase of 18 units took place at 210° and at 350° a further increase of 400 units indicated that probably two molecules of ligand are affected. Similar investigation of $\text{Cu}_2\text{Fln}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ showed that at 120° the increase of 20 units roughly corresponded to 1.5 molecules of water. A further increase of 16 units at 200° indicated that one more molecule of water is let off due to heating.

The slight difference in the thermal stabilities of the two complexes appears to be related to the bridging hydroxy groups. $\text{Cu}_8(\text{Flcn})_5(\text{OH})_8 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_8$ has hydroxy bridging of much more complexity than the other compound. It may be noted that no sooner these bridges are removed due to formation of water the complex virtually breaks down.

There is ample evidence in literature that Cu(II) forms polymeric complexes which offer serious obstacles in studying them especially because they are insoluble in normal solvents and hence escape the determination of molecular weight^{8,12,13}. The mass-spectra method is of no avail as these complexes are non-volatile and melt or decompose in the range 250°–350°. Some of the complexes, not only of copper but of nickel, cobalt etc., were characterised as polymers merely from elemental and spectral analysis¹³. That these complexes of Cu(II) are polymeric could be established only on the sound observation of Fernelius¹⁴ that all known dimers of copper(II) were soluble in normal solvents. The copper(II) complexes prepared in the present investigation were insoluble in all known common solvents and a very low solubility (10^{-2} to 10^{-3} M) in DMF, CH_3CN and CH_3NO_2 indirectly suggested their polymeric nature. The brown or brownish red colours of the complexes seem to be characteristic of a polymeric complex is seen in the chlorocuprate and other polymeric compounds of Cu(II). Again, the pH at which these complexes were formed as red brown precipitates suggests that these complexes went polymeric through hydroxybridging, which in turn was responsible for pronounced lowering of magnetic moment of Cu(II), in these complexes.

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